

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF MACHINE LEARNING AND DEEP LEARNING METHODS FOR SKIN CANCER DETECTION

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ABSTRACT

The application of Machine Learning (ML) methods to diagnose diseases has emerged as a highly significant topic of interest in medical field. Among various diseases, skin cancer is one of the most dangerous types of cancer and remains a leading cause of death worldwide. Early diagnosis is crucial to reduce mortality rates. Traditionally, skin cancer is diagnosed via visual scanning procedures by dermatologists, which is subjective and error prone. To tackle these issues, ML based methods have been proposed to assist dermatologist in the early and accurate diagnosis. This paper presents a comprehensive systematic review of ML and Deep Learning (DL) methods used for the early detection of skin cancer. It analyses research papers published in reputed journals that focus on skin cancer diagnosis. The analysis covers multiple aspects including type of skin disease studied, data set used, data processing techniques, data augmentation methods, models utilized for skin disease recognition, and performance of these models. Research findings are summarized and illustrated in the form of graphs and tables to facilitate a better understanding of the current landscape. Additionally, this paper discusses the current challenges in employing ML methods for skin cancer diagnosis and provides insights into potential future directions.

Index terms: Machine learning, deep learning, skin disease, segmentation, image Classification

1. INTRODUCTION

Skin is the largest organ of the human body. The main function of the skin is to protect the human body from external harmful substances and prevent the loss of vital nutrients [1]. Skin health is influenced by various factors including solar radiation, environmental conditions, smoking, viruses, and sports activities. These factors can compromise the skin's functionality, inflict damage, adversely affect overall health and in severe cases, pose a threat to life [2]. Therefore, skin disease has become one of the common diseases of human beings. Skin cancer is one of the most common types of cancer that begins with the uncontrolled reproduction of skin cells. Skin cancer is one of the primary reasons for deaths worldwide and it affects people across all cultures and age groups.

Skin cancer is divided into melanoma and nonmelanoma skin cancer. Melanoma is a hazardous, rare, and deadly type of skin cancer. Melanoma develops in cells called melanocytes. It starts when healthy melanocytes begin to grow out of control, creating a cancerous tumor. It can affect any area of the human body and appears on the areas exposed to sun rays such as on face, hands, neck, lips, etc. Melanoma cancers can only be cured if diagnosed early, otherwise they spread to other body parts and lead to the victim's painful death. According to the Global Cancer Observatory (GLOBOCAN) estimates, there were 19,3

million incident cancer cases worldwide for the year 2020 [3]. India ranked third after China and USA. GLOBOCAN predicted that cancer cases in India would increase to 2.08million, accounting for a rise of 57.7 percent in 2040 from 2020 [4].

Skin cancer is typically diagnosed by visual screening with an accuracy of about 60% [5]. The diagnostic accuracy rate of skin cancer increases to 89% using dermoscopy images [6]. Although dermoscopy diagnosis skin cancer with better accuracy, it is not suited for diagnosing early melanoma, and there is still a need to improve classification accuracy to increase survival rate of patients. The problem with dermoscopy and the need to increase the diagnostic accuracy of skin cancer further laid the foundation for developing computer-aided detection methods for diagnosing skin cancers. Computer Aided Diagnosis (CAD) system had six major phases for skin cancer diagnosis: image acquisition, preprocessing, segmentation, feature extraction, feature selection, and classification [7]. Each phase has its unique role in skin cancer diagnosis.

Deep Learning (DL) algorithms have revolutionized the entire landscape of Machine Learning (ML) during recent decades. These algorithms are inspired by the function and structure of the human brain. DL algorithms are implemented in a broad range of areas such as computer vision, pattern recognition, semantic segmentation, and bioinformatics. As compared to ML approaches, DL methods have shown impressive results in these applications. This paper thoroughly discusses and analyze skin cancer detection methods based on ML, Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and DL. A significant amount of research has been performed on this topic. Thus, it is important to accumulate and analyze the studies, categorize them, and summarize the available research findings. The research focused on publications on reputed journals and conferences. Many papers were collected, thoroughly evaluated and analyzed from different aspects. Although many intelligent techniques developed for skin cancer diagnosis, there is still space for further improvement in present diagnostic techniques.

This paper is segmented into four sections. Section 2 presents a detail of dataset used for skin cancer diagnosis. Section 3 discusses the skin cancer detection methods using Artificial neural network methods. Section 4 describes deep learning methods for skin cancer diagnosis. Section 5 summarizes the whole study and presents a brief conclusion.

2. SKIN CANCER DATASETS

There are three types of images are used for the identification and categorization of skin cancers: clinical images, dermoscopy images, and histopathology images. This paper focuses on dermoscopy images, as this type is easy to retrieve and is used widely by dermatologist, and there is a good amount of public data for researchers. The International Skin Imaging Collaboration (ISIC) [8] is the main provider of publicly accessible databases. Table.1 lists databases for skin cancer diagnosis. Figure.1 shows sample images form the HAM1000 dataset [9] with different types of skin cancers.

Table.1 Skin cancer databases

Dataset name	Year	Image quantity	Publicly accessible	Reference
ISIC 2020	2020	33,126	✓	[8]
ISIC 2019	2019	25,331	✓	[8]
HAM10000	2018	10,015	✓	[9]
ISIC 2017	2017	1372	✓	[8]
PH2	2013	200	✓	[9]
Atlas	2000	1024	✓	[15]
DermQuest	1999	22,082	✓	[25]

Figure.1 Skin diseases from HAM10000

3. ML BASED SKIN CANCER DETECTION APPROACHES

ANN is a non-linear network and its structure is inspired by the biological structure of the human brain. It typically consists of three layers. Input layer, hidden layers, and output layer. ANN is used for the classification of extracted features in skin cancer diagnosis. In ANN

based method, input images are preprocessed using image processing techniques to improve quality of the images. Following this, a variety of features are computed and then fed as input to the ANN for classification. In ANN, input layer accepts features and then transfer them to the hidden layers. Hidden layer process the input data and pass it to the output layer. The network is trained using training algorithm to fine-tune the weights of the network. After successful training, the network is employed to detect skin diseases.

Kanimozhi et al. [11] proposed a CAD system for skin cancer diagnosis. The proposed system used ANN to classify skin images as melanoma or non-melanoma. Dermoscopic images were converted into grayscale images and lesion region was extracted. Asymmetry, Border, Colour, Diameter (ABCD) features were computed and then fed to ANN. The network was trained with Back Propagation (BP) to classify images. Xie et al. [12] designed a skin cancer detection system using Neural Network Ensemble (NNE) model. Initially, a self-generating NN was utilized to isolate lesions from its background. Secondly, a total of 57 features including tumor border, color, and texture were extracted. Thirdly, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed to choose optimal features. Finally, NNE was adopted to categorize images as benign or malignant. NNE improved classification performance compared to Random Forest (RF) and Support Vector Machine (SVM).

Dorj et al. [13] used SVM and AlexNET for skin disease diagnosis. Input images were gathered and then cropped to remove unwanted regions. A pretrained AlexNet was employed to compute feature from the preprocessed images. The obtained features were used as input for the SVM to classify as squamous cell carcinoma or basal cell carcinoma, melanoma, and actinic keratosis and attained an accuracy of 95.1%. Chatterjee et al. [14] implemented a system that used ML model for multiclass classification. The system extracted various features such as shape, border, regularity, texture, and color and used Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) for feature selection. Finally, SVM classifier with Radial Basis Function (RBF) was employed to perform categorization.

Rajasekar et al. [15] classified dermoscopic images using Spectral Graph Wavelet Transform (SGWT) and K-nearest Neighbor (KNN). Images were processed with SGWT to extract texture features. The obtained features were classified as normal or abnormal using KNN. Authors used ISIC dataset to test the efficacy of their model and reported an accuracy of 96.79%. Melanoma is the most common type of skin cancer. Several methods have been developed to aid in early detection. However, accurately detecting skin cancer remains a very difficult task. Amin et al. [16] outlined a three-phase approach for skin cancer detection. Primarily, skin images were resided and then converted into Lab color space. Secondly, 2-D wavelet transform and otsu thresholding were utilized to separate the skin lesions. Finally, Ensemble KNN was employed to detect melanoma images.

Baygin et al. [17] presented an automatic model for skin cancer detection. In this model, multilevel texture features were generated using Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) and deep features were obtained using pretrained Darknet. Neighborhood Component Analysis (NCA) was adopted to reduce the dimensionality of features. Finally, SVM performed the classification task with an accuracy of 91.53%. Kanca and Ayas [18] presented a ML model for skin disease classification. Skin images were preprocessed using filters to eliminate noise and then cropped to discard redundant region. Some features like color, shape, and texture features were extracted from the preprocessed ISIC dataset. These obtained features are categorized using KNN.

Tembhurne et al. [19] introduced a skin cancer detection model by fusing ML and DL. Authors used contourlet transform and Local Binary Pattern (LBP) to extract hand crafted features and then PCA was utilized to select relevant features. Linear SVM was employed to distinguish between melanoma and non-melanoma and reported an accuracy of 93%. Keerthana et al. [20] detected skin cancer using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and

SVM. This approach consisted of feature extraction and classification. The CNN was used for extracting deep features from input images. The obtained deep features were fed to the SVM for image categorization. A summary of reviewed papers is tabulated in Table.3.

Table.2 ML models used for skin disease diagnosis

Researchers	Year	Features	Classifier	No. of images/ Dataset	Number of classes	Accuracy (%)
Kanimozhi et al. [11]	2016	ABCD	ANN	31	2	96.9
Xie et al. [12]	2017	Texture, color, Border	NNE	135	2	88.1
Dorj et al. [13]	2018	AlexNet	SVM	3753	4	95.1
Chatterjee et al, [14]	2019	GLCM	SVM	ISIC	3	96.52
Rajasekar et al. [15]	2020	SGWT	KNN	ISIC	2	96.79
Amin et al. [16]	2020	Wavelet features	Ensemble KNN	PH2	2	98.71
Baygin et al. [17]	2022	Textural	SVM	3297	2	91.53
Kanca and Ayas [18]	2022		KNN	ISIC	2	88
Tembhurne et al. [19]	2023	LBP	Linear SVM	ISIC	2	93
Keerthana et al. [20]	2023	CNN	SVM	ISBI 2016	2	86.23

4. DEEP LEARNING BASED SKIN CANCER DETECTION APPROACHES

A CNN is an essential type of DL and can be effectively used for computer vision tasks. It is used for image classification and image recognition. CNN consists of multiple convolutional layers, pooling layer and that are followed by one or more fully connected layer. The major strength of CNN is that the network itself learn features from input images during training. CNN based approaches have attained remarkable performance in object detection, segmentation, pattern recognition, and classification.

Ali and Marzouqi [21] proposed a LightNet for melanoma detection. A light CNN having 17 layers was used in the feature extraction process to improve classification rate. The proposed method utilized softmax classification for classification and showed 81.6% accuracy in melanoma detection. Esteva et al. [22] conducted research on skin disease detection and classification using pretrained GoogleNet. The network achieved performance on par with all tested cases, showing DL was capable of categorizing skin disease with a level of competence comparable to dermatologists.

A ResNet-152 for categorizing 12 different types of skin disease was presented by Mendes et al. [23]. The DL model was trained on 3797 images to detect skin disease. Augmentation based on scale transformation was applied to improve performance. The model achieved an accuracy of 91% in classifying skin disease. Harangi et al. [24] introduced an ensemble of DL by using CNNs, AlexNet, VGGNet, and GoogleNet to detect skin disease.

Performance of the model was tested on International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging (ISBI) dataset. An ensemble network outperformed all other individual networks.

Hasan et al. [25] implemented a skin disease detection system using image processing techniques and CNN. In this system, images were converted into grayscale image to make them fit for feature extraction and classification. A CNN was used for feature extraction and softmax was used for classification. A 2-layer CNN for classification of 2 skin diseases was introduced by Albahar [26]. The architecture consisted of two convolution layers followed by a pooling and dropout layers. After dropout layer, fully connected layer with 128 neurons was used followed by softmax classifier to distinguish between benign and malignant lesions. Each convolutional layer had a regularizer to determine the values of filter in order to boost the classification rate.

Acosta et al. [27] designed an automated system for skin disease detection. The proposed system consisted of two phases. In phase 1, mask and region-based CNN was used to crop the lesion region from the dermatoscopic images. In phase 2, ResNet152 was employed to categorize the images into benign or malignant. The results showed a significant improvement compared to earlier methods. A comparative study between six different Transfer Learning (TL) nets for multiclass skin disease classification was done by Jain et al. [28]. Skin lesion images were gathered from the HAM10000 dataset. Six TL nets namely VGG19, ResNet50, InceptionV3, MobileNet, InceptionResNetV2, and Xception were used for analysis. Results showed that Xception net outperformed the other networks with an accuracy of 90.48%. Similar to this, Sagar and Dheeba [30] used three pretrained networks, including inception v3, inceptionResNetv2, and ResNet 50 for skin disease classification. Results showed that the classification rate of ResNet50 was 93.5%, InceptionV3 was 89.3%, and InceptionResNetv2 was 90.7%.

Tabrizchi et al. [31] implemented a CNN based on deep network for melanoma detection. The model was trained on ISIC dataset attained an accuracy of 90%. The performance of the model was compared with other DL methods, with the proposed model performing better. A novel hybrid CNN model for skin cancer detection was designed Hasan et al. [32]. The model was developed by fusing preprocessing techniques and hybrid-CNN to detect skin lesions. The model consisted of three processes such as preprocessing, feature learning, and classification. In the preprocessing phase, lesion segmentation and augmentation methods were used to process dermoscopic images. In feature learning, three CNNs were designed with different architectures to learn feature from the preprocessed images. Finally, ensemble classifier performed the categorization task.

An interesting approach based on reinforcement learning for skin disease detected was introduced by Barata et al. [33]. Authors used reinforcement learning to implement non-uniform incentives and penalties using expert-generated labels. The approach was tested on ISIC dataset and reported an accuracy of 88%. The reinforcement learning based model improved sensitivity compared to supervised learning models. Gilani et al. [34] developed a spiking VGG 13 network for skin disease detection. The model is better suited for hardware implementation as spiking neural networks are more energy efficient than their ANN counterparts. The model was trained on HAM10000 dataset and reported an average classification rate 89.75%. A summary of recent works on skin cancer detection using DL is reflected in Table.3.

Table.3 DL models used for skin disease diagnosis

Researchers	Year	Classifier	No. of images/ Dataset	Number of classes	Accuracy (%)
Ali and Marzouqi [21]	2017	LightNet	ISIC 2016	2	81.6
Esteva et al. [22]	2017	GoogleNet	ISIC	4	72.1
Mendes et al. [23]	2018	CNN-ResNet 152	1470	12	91
Harangi et al. [24]	2018	Ensemble of DL	DerIS and DermQuest	3	83.8
Hasan et al. [25]	2019	CNN	ISIC	2	89.5
Albahar [26]	2019	2-layer CNN	ISIC	2	97.49
Acosta et al. [27]	2020	CNN with ResNet 152	2742	2	90.4
Jain et al. [28]	2021	TL based nets	HAM10000	2	90.48
Ho et al. [29]	2021	Purned Resnet 18	297	2	80
Sagar and Dheebea [30]	2021	ResNet 50 wit TL	ISIC	2	93.5
Tabrizchi et al. [31]	2022	CNN	ISIC	2	90
Hasan et al. [32]	2022	Hybrid CNN	ISIC	7	90.2
Barata et al. [33]	2023	Reinforcement learning	ISIC	7	88
Gilani et al. [34]	2023	Spiking VGG-13	HAM10000	2	89.75

5. OPEN CHALLENGES AND DISCUSSION

Numerous studies based on ML and DL based skin cancer detection have been devoted and have demonstrated excellent performance. Before ML and DL is utilized to detect skin cancer in clinical circumstances, there are still a number of issues that need more attention. These issues are discussed below:

Data issue

DL based approaches employed small amount of data for training and validation compared with images for other popular DL tasks. ISIC offers the largest dataset of skin diseases, containing tens of thousands of images. While it is possible to collect vast amount of data on skin cancer from web or hospitals, categorizing these images requires professional expertise. It is challenging and expensive. DL models require substantial amount of data for training and minor adjustments can lead to overfitting. Given these challenges, future research should prioritize developing DL models that need less data.

Interclass variation

Medical images exhibit very small interclass variation. For instance, the difference between melanoma and non-melanoma skin disease is much less. Further to this, differentiating between a birthmark and melanoma is quite challenging. This limited variation complicates the tasks of medical image analysis and classification.

Image quality

Most dermoscopic skin cancer images are collected utilizing high-resolution cameras in controlled environments. ML and DL trained on these images can exhibit excellent diagnostic performance. However, these models may struggle to achieve the same performance

when analyzing skin images taken with low-resolution cameras under varying lighting conditions. ML and DL models are highly sensitive to the camera specifications used for acquiring images. Additionally, self-captured images often suffer from poor quality and noise. Consequently, detecting skin diseases with ML or DL becomes challenging due to the noise introduced by data from various sources.

Model generalization

Generalization of model is an active area of research in skin disease diagnosis. Most studies relied on medical imaging technology. When models are applied to images taken with other devices like smart phones, there is a significant drop in performance. In such case, transfer learning can be beneficial when an appropriate training data is unavailable. Another research focus is the robustness of skin disease detection. Large training sets with high-quality and high-resolution images have led to models that are less resilient to noise and other factors.

Unbalanced data

Real-world dermoscopic images for skin disease detection are highly imbalanced. These datasets have uneven distribution of images for different types of skin cancer. For instance, they may have more images for common skin disease but only a few for rare types. This unbalanced data makes it challenging to generalized from the visual features of images.

Lack of hardware

High-performance hardware with substantial GPU power is essential to extract distinct features from images to improve skin cancer detection. The scarcity of such high computing power presents a significant challenge in training DL models for diagnosing skin diseases.

6. CONCLUSION

This review study explored the use of ML and DL techniques for the early diagnosis of skin cancer. The efficacy and performance of these models in skin cancer diagnosis have been validated via comprehensive analysis of various studies. ML-based approaches have used specific image processing techniques for preprocessing, segmentation, and feature extraction. Results have revealed that the both ML and DL methods can effectively detect skin diseases using diverse datasets. Compared to ML based approaches, DL models have shown promising performance by visualizing visual information with greater accuracy. Furthermore, DL models are needed for complex and multi-model processing tasks such as image cropping, resizing, and pixel-level adjustments. The review has emphasized the need for a fully automated system to skin disease diagnosis to reduce the time required for precise detection. It also highlighted the application of DL models in detecting skin disease. Additionally, this review discussed some of the challenges for skin disease detection including data limitation, unbalanced data, image quality, model generalization, and lack of powerful hardware.

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